

CUSTOMER LOYALTY AND SALES PROMOTION OF NIGERIAN BREWERY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814693>

Abstract: The study examined the association between customers' loyalty and the sales promotion of Nigerian Brewery. Survey research was employed for the study. Data for the study were generated from the questionnaire administered to the respondents (staff of the Brewery). The hypotheses were tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance with aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20.0. Findings of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between corporate image loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery. It was also found out that a significant relationship exist between behavioural loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others, that strategies that boost emotional loyalty, such as product adverts should always strive to be in line with product functionality; and salespeople should always be encouraged to base arguments on actual product functions, not fictitious claims.

Keyword: Customer loyalty, Cooperate image and behavioural and Sale promotion

Introduction

Customers are persons (for instance, individuals) or corporate bodies that purchase goods and/or services from the market to meet their needs and wants (Khadka & Maharjan, 2017). According to Ndubisi and Nwankwo (2019), customers are the reason for the continued existence of an organization. These market stakeholders purchase goods and/or services that are able to satisfy needs or wants at a fair competitive price. This pre-condition determines the continuous patronage of a particular brand which drives the consequent development of loyalty by genuinely satisfied customers. This is responsible for maintaining sustainable business performance in the long run (Ndubisi & Nwankwo, 2019). According to Kleinig (2022) loyalty may be "characterized as a practical disposition to persist in an intrinsically valued (though not necessarily valuable) associational attachment". The Oxford Dictionary simply put it as "a strong feeling of support or allegiance".

The success of an organization depends upon the satisfaction of the customers. For a company, customers always come prior to the profits. If the customers will not be satisfied with the product or the service, then the company will not earn profits as there will not be much sale. Sales performance describes the comparison of a company's income in a certain period, which if there is an increase in profits, then the company's management will become

easier (Zia & Shahzad, 2015). Based on its usefulness, customer loyalty has an important role for a business owner in introducing products or services and building communication with customers through various types of platforms (Chaffey & Chadwick, 2019). The company that will fully understand the interests and needs of customers so that such customers are fully satisfied will remain at the top position in the market. Customer satisfaction is a vital component in the success of the company and it also helps in the expansion. In general, customers are the people who buy the product or service to fulfill the needs and want that meet those expectations. Therefore, companies should determine the price of the product with good quality in order to attract the customers in order to maintain long term relationship.

Quite a number of studies has been conducted on customer satisfaction and firm performance in both local and foreign countries. There is however scarcity of research studies in customer loyalty and sales performance. Studies like Belem, Alireza and Hugo (2023) analyzed the impact of packaging-free practices in food retail stores, particularly supermarkets on customer loyalty. Vikas, Kyuhong, Carly, Markus, Muzeeb, Narendra and Shrihari (2023) synthesized research on the relationship of customer satisfaction with customer. Rizwan, Tanveer and Hammad (2022) inspected the intervention of customer satisfaction in the association between service quality and corporate image to customer loyalty in the Pakistan banking sector. Akshita, Jatin, Lovika, Mehul and Shikha (2021) determined the relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty and the factors influencing these concepts. Ogunyemi (2019) investigated the impact of customer loyalty on organizational performance in the hotel industry. Ndubisi and Nwankwo (2019) examined the nexus of customer satisfaction and organizational performance. Kabu and Soniya (2017) examined customer satisfaction provided by Trivsel and customer loyalty received by Trivsel from its customers. In a prior related study, Solomon et al. (2017) evaluated the influence of direct selling strategies on customer loyalty. Magatef and Tomalieh (2015) investigated the impact of loyalty programs on customer retention in Jordan. Soltanmoradi, Poor, and Nazari (2013) examined the influence of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty on firm performance. However, Nosike and Egbunike (2022) and Okonji, Olayemi, and Oghojafor (2018) ascertained the relationship between customers' loyalty and the sales performance and sales volume respectively. None of these prior studies maintained concise focus on the subject of discourse.

The study also established a scope gap, which buttresses the fact that there is a limited study on customer loyalty and sale performance in Nigeria. Moreso, studies conducted by Nosike and Egbunike (2022) and Okonji, Olayemi, and Oghojafor (2018) were not just the only studies that sought to ascertain the relationship between customers' loyalty and the sales performance and sales volume respectively but were also the only studies that were carried out in the manufacturing sector. This study was conducted on Nigerian Brewery, Enugu. Specifically, this study ascertains the relationship between corporate image loyalty, behavioural Loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery

Conceptual Review

Customer Loyalty

A customer is said to be loyal when such a customer always prefer to rebuy a particular brand in the midst of other competing brands. This suggests that the loyalty of a customer can be inferred from a customer's deeply held commitment to repurchase a preferred product or service consistently in the future. This commitment causes a customer to repeatedly search for the same brand set to purchase despite situational influences and marketing efforts that has the potential to cause switching behaviour. Customers' loyalty is a multidimensional construct with attitude and behaviour as its major components, In fact, customers' loyalty describes an ongoing emotional

relationship between a firm and customer. The loyalty of a customer is manifest by the willingness of a customer to engage with and repeatedly purchase from a firm instead of its competitor. This implies that loyalty is a by-product of a customer's positive experience with a firm and thereafter creates trust.

Leninkumar (2017) remarked that customer loyalty is an important factor that enables firms enjoys competitive advantage over other firms even under a highly competitive and dynamic environment. In the same vein, Oliver (2019) asserts that customer loyalty is a promise of buyers to purchase particular products, services and brands of an organization over a consistent period of time, irrespective of competitor's new products and innovations. It is also common to observe that loyal customers perceive the organization in a positive light, recommend the firm to others and engage in product/service repurchase (Dimitriades, 2016). This makes loyal customers the prime source of generating profits and attracting new customers to a firm. The implication is that loyal customers are assets to marketers. In fact, the activities of loyal customers have impact on repeat purchases, word of mouth recommendations and customer retention. Customer loyalty is the habit of a customer preferring a particular product over another to satisfy his or her need (Ranabhat, 2018). According to Al Jamil (2021), this is also regardless of pricing or location factors. This is consistent with the Newman and Werbel (1973) age-long definition, which explained that loyal customers constantly purchase a brand, in the short and long term, without any intention of seeking alternative brand-related information.

Consumer loyalty is a powerful influencer such that any loyal customer would be less likely to switch to alternative brands from factors such as price increases or other special promotional effects (Yoo & Bai, 2013). They even often end up attracting new customers to the brand via "word of mouth" marketing thus making a lesser expensive market segment to maintain. Loyal and satisfied clients will not be hesitant to spread the good word about the benefits of the products they use (Tamaruddin, Firdaus, & Endri, 2020). Customer loyalty is not a one-off thing but is achieved over time through multiple transactions (Khadka & Maharjan, 2017). Loyalty requires the company to focus on value creation via its products/services and to show a genuine interest in building relationships with customers (Griffin, 2002). Customer loyalty is one of the most frequently addressed subjects in the manufacturing industry. The subject has gained attention of other service organization because of its importance to the successful running of any business (Ogunyemi, 2019). Realizing the prime importance of customer loyalty to organizations, a major concern is to determine how it affects the –overall performance in the industry. Issues involving customer loyalty in service organizations have drawn the attention of various researchers concerned with finding the determination of customer loyalty and their implications in the organization (Heskett & Sasser, 2010)

Corporate Image Loyalty

Corporate image is defined as perceptions of an organization reflected in the associations held in consumer memory (Keller, 1993). It is the sum of people's perceptions of an organization. Images and perceptions are created through all the senses: sight, sound, smell, touch, tastes and feelings experienced through product usage, customer service, the commercial environment and corporate communications (Smith & Taylor, 2004). It is external perception of all human and physical resources of an organization, especially characteristics as employees' behaviours and attitudes, communication levels, clothing et cetera (Pampaloni, 2006). It is defined as the perception of an organization that customers' hold in their memories. Because it works as a filter through which a company's whole operation is perceived, a corporate image reflects a company's overall reputation and prestige (Kim & Lee, 2011).

It is obvious that corporate image is concerned with the impression an organization forms in consumers' minds and the perception of consumers arising from this impression. It is therefore essential that GSM operators show concern about the way it is perceived by their variety of stakeholders such as employees, customers, shareholders, government, media, and the general public, as this affects initial and repeat purchase. The role of corporate image is pivotal in today's business environment (Gioia, Schultz & Corley, 2000). A positive and reinforcing corporate image is capable of generating customer satisfaction and loyalty in organizations. Corporate and brand image have also emerged as determinants of customer loyalty. There is a relationship between corporate image, customer satisfaction and loyalty. A well-managed corporate identity unconsciously reassures customers (Smith & Taylor, 2004). Corporate image is influenced both by service quality and customer satisfaction, which in turn influences customer loyalty (Kandampully, 2007). The high point of the above discussion is that the reassurance keeps customers coming to do a repeat business and lock them into loyalty.

Behavioural Loyalty

A critical review of literature reveals that the consequences of customer's behaviour are always of immense benefits to the organization. Also, loyal customers are so dogmatic that these customers will not switch even in the midst of the organization apparent errors. However, Ball, Coelho and Machas (2014) identified behaviour loyalty and attitude loyalty as common dimensions of customer's loyalty. Behaviour loyalty is seen as repeated transactions, percentage of total transactions and total expenditures. In simple terms, behaviour loyalty is repeated purchase. A customer behavioural loyalty connotes customer's purchase intention (Mellens, Dekimpe & Steenkamp, 2016). Behaviour loyalty of a customer can result in the generation of profit through increase in market shares (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2011).

Behavioral loyalty is a form of repeat purchase behavior (Khadka & Maharjan, 2017). According to Encyclopedia (2016) behavioral loyalty is when a customer continues to buy/use a particular product, service or brand (at least as much as before). Behavioral loyalty is defined as the customer's intention to repurchase and patronize the product or service (Chaudhuri & Holbrook, 2001). Behavioral Loyalty is vital for a company in order to generate profitability (Kumari & Patyal, 2017). The ability of a corporation to create profits depends heavily on its consumers' behavioral loyalty (Inegbedion & Obadiaru, 2019). For instance, Obasan et al. (2015) in Nigeria found that brand loyalty positively correlated with organizational profitability. Also, Kumari and Patyal (2017) on a sample of Indian patients argue that behavior loyalty would yield attitudinal effects in public health care.

Sales analysis (SA) is the process of collecting, evaluating and applying data about various sales processes. For instance, sales data can tell businesses about sales numbers, revenue values, customer retention and acquisition rates and overall profitability. SA sales analysis is an effective tool that managers can use according to several methods, all with the goal of providing a wider perspective of sales activities. You can track sales performance metrics, analyze them and identify aspects of your organization's practices that support sales and sales processes that need improvement. Sales performance is an increase in sales that occurs from year to year. Sales performance can indicate the level of consumer demand for the company's products (Kouser, Bano, & Azeem, 2012) Companies that experience sales growth means that the company's products are accepted by the market and successfully compete with competitors (Delmar, McKelvie, & Wennberg, 2013). The company can increase its efficiency and productivity through sales growth. By knowing how high the sales growth rate is, the company can predict the profits to be received. Companies can set profit targets so that they have a clear direction in achieving goals.

Sales promotion has been taunted as one of the strategies that is capable of enabling an organization achieve improved growth in sales there beating competition in the short run as well as prospering in the long run. The growth in sales promotion efforts could be attributed to many factors. These include; increased impulse purchase, the rising cost of advertising clutter, shortening time horizons, increased competition, and price conscious customer searching for deals among others (Smith & Zook, 2011). Kotler and Keller (2009) reported that the Sales Promotional budget of most organization has increased to over 75% of the total communication budget over the last twenty years. The acceptance of Sales Promotion as a basic tool for increases can be attributed to increase in the number of brands, increase in the frequency of competitor use of Sales Promotion, perception of similarity between brands, increase in consumer price orientation, decrease in advertising efficiency and the demand for more deals from manufacturers (Okonji, Olayemi & Oghojafor, 2018).

Empirical studies

Ekankumo (2023) examined the impact of marketing mix elements on brand loyalty in Nigerian telecommunication firms. The general objective is to examine the impact of marketing mix elements on brand loyalty in Nigerian telecommunication firms. A stratified sampling technique was used to select the respondents in each of the selected telecommunication firms in Asaba. Findings revealed the extent to which price, distribution, promotion and product affect brand loyalty. The study concludes that distribution strategy has a significant relationship with product management. Belem, Alireza and Hugo (2023) analyzed the impact of packaging-free practices in food retail stores, particularly supermarkets, on customer loyalty. Based on the literature on the impacts of sustainable practices and corporate social responsibility (CSR) policies on consumer behavior, this study defined a set of seven hypotheses that were tested using data collected from 447 consumers that regularly buy food products at supermarkets. The data were subjected to structural equation modeling using Smart PLS. This study found out that packaging-free practices positively influence brand image, brand trust, satisfaction and customer loyalty. The expected positive impacts of brand image and satisfaction on customer loyalty were also confirmed. Zelina and Eriana (2022) obtained empirical evidence related to the development of social media marketing (SMM) activities to improve sales performance through Instagram as the main marketing channel. This study uses a deductive approach to the research subject, namely the Sprinkdays business, which is engaged in the culinary field with the object of research in social media marketing activities and sales performance. The data analysis technique used descriptive statistics to get an overview of the implementation of social media marketing and inferential statistics through a paired t-test on the action research results carried out. The results showed that the development of social media marketing activities through customer feedback, communication, content sharing, and customer relationships applied to the Sprinkdays Instagram account did not increase the sales performance of the Sprinkdays business. Nosike and Egbunike (2022) ascertained the relationship between customers' loyalty and the sales performance of Dangote Cement products in Awka, Anambra State. The study specifically examined the relationship between emotional loyalty and consumer purchase intention; and, the relationship between behavioral loyalty and consumer purchase intention of Dangote cement. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses were tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The results showed a positive significant relationship between emotional loyalty and consumer purchase intention; and, a positive significant relationship between behavioral loyalty and consumer purchase intention. Haryadi, Haerofiatna and Alfariz (2022) examined and analyses the factors in increasing consumer loyalty to after-sales service through customer loyalty. This research was conducted at PT. Tunas Toyota Cilegon Banten with a population of 1102, and then the sample used was 150 respondents. The

questionnaire method was distributed using an interval scale of 1 strongly disagree to 10 strongly agree. The data analysis technique used SEM PLS. The results of this study indicate the effect of after-sales service on consumer loyalty, the influence of after-sales service on customer satisfaction, the influence of customer satisfaction on consumer loyalty, and customer satisfaction can be a mediation in increasing consumer loyalty. Akshita, Jatin, Lovika, Mehul and Shikha (2021) determined the relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty and the factors influencing these concepts. Further the study will get to know that how these concepts affect the relationship that customers have with the organization that helps the organization to be at a better place in the market or beat the competitors. The relationship between satisfaction and loyalty influences the profits. The more customer is satisfied, the more loyal towards the brand. A loyal customer leads to an increase in both sales and profitability. Customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between customer loyalty and service quality. Herman, Joyce, and Andi (2020) determined whether there is an influence of the four variables above with trust in suppliers and to find out whether trust in suppliers can be a mediating variable for the four variables on customer loyalty. The research took a sample of 100 people using the SEM-PLS test. The result of supplier performance showed (1) in a product, and sales service quality, technical improvement services, and complaint handling services had a significant effect on trust in suppliers; (2) trust in suppliers had a significant effect on customer loyalty. Rashid, Nurunnabi, Rahman and Kaium Masud (2020) explores whether the service qualities have any impact on customer loyalty. The study uses both primary and secondary data to conclude the research objectives. A survey of 356 questionnaires was carried out among the customers of the selected Islamic banks of Bangladesh to gather information regarding customer service quality and customer loyalty, while financial performance data were attained from the annual reports. The study empirically documents a positively significant impact of service quality (tangibles, empathy, reliability, and responsiveness) on customer loyalty, while assurance shows an insignificant relationship. Furthermore, the study does not find any significant relationship between customer loyalty and the financial performance of Bangladeshi Islamic Banks. Ndubisi and Nwankwo (2019) examined the nexus of customer satisfaction and organizational performance. The study adopted the survey design. The study used a sample of firms from the Nigerian banking industry,. The sample comprised 264 customers and 12 staff of six banks (First Bank, Fidelity Bank, United Bank for Africa, Zenith Bank, Diamond Bank and Access Bank) in the five south-eastern states. The study utilized primary data; obtained from the administration of questionnaires. The hypotheses were tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and Kendall's coefficient of concordance test. The results revealed a significant relationship between customers' feelings of banks' services meeting their expectations and banks' financial services acceptability; and, a significant relationship between banks' staff feelings of customers' satisfaction with bank services and banks retaining customers profitably. Soltanmoradi, Poor, and Nazari (2013) examined the influence of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty on firm performance. They surveyed a large sample of 196 students in Tehran, Iran. The study adopted a survey and descriptive-causal research design. The results showed a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and trust, and commitment. There is also a positive relationship between customer loyalty and firm performance; and, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Adeleke and Aminu (2012) investigate the determinants of customer loyalty in the GSM market in Nigeria. Primary data was obtained through a questionnaire. 252 questionnaires were self-administered by the researchers to the subscribers of the four major GSM providers in Lagos State. 198 of the questionnaires were returned, properly filled. The findings revealed that service quality, customer satisfaction, and corporate image are important determinants of customer satisfaction and loyalty in the Nigeria's GSM market. The fourth factor, price/tariff is found not to be a determinant of customer satisfaction

and loyalty in market. A conclusion was drawn to the effect that since factors influencing customer loyalty have been established, GSM companies should note these and emphasize them in their marketing strategy.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design in which data were collected across sampled segment of the population. This design is also preferred as it makes enough provision for protection against bias and maximizes reliability (Boniface & Ambrose 2015). Furthermore, survey is considered best research design suitable for collection of data from large sample of respondents since individual are the unit of analysis.

The population of the study covered the staff of Nigerian Brewery, Enugu. The elements of the population were the sales team and production team. Due to the size of the population and its possible accessibility, the study used purposive sampling technique to adopt the entire population comprising 46 respondents as the sample size of the study.

Data were collected by means of survey using copies of structured questionnaire as research instrument. The instrument was coded in five-point Likert rating scale format as follows; Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The questionnaire dealt with essential issues concerning relationship between customer loyalty and sales promotion in Nigerian Brewery, Enugu.

Method of Data Analysis

In testing the hypotheses formulated, data were analyzed using Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance with aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20.0. This method was adopted so as to ascertain the strength of the relationship, patterns, significant connections, and trends between the variables in the hypotheses.

Mathematical formula for Correlation Coefficient is stated as;

$$r = \frac{N\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[N\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][N\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

- N = number of pairs of scores
- $\sum xy$ = Sum of the products of paired scores
- $\sum x$ = Sum of x scores
- $\sum y$ = Sum of y scores
- $\sum x^2$ = Sum of squared x scores
- $\sum y^2$ = Sum of squared y scores

Decision rule:

Accept the alternative hypothesis when the probability value (p-value) is less than alpha value of 0.05, otherwise reject.

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Out of four six (46) copies of questionnaire administered, forty three (43) were completed and returned, this represent 87%.

Table 1: Responses Summary on customer loyalty, Behavioural loyalty and sales promotion

Statements	SA	A	Un	D	SD
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Corporate image loyalty					
It is clear that corporate image refers to the impression an organization leaves on the minds of consumers.	14	22	0	7	0
A well-maintained corporate identity subconsciously reassures customers	10	16	2	10	5
The company's reputation is affected by both service quality and customer satisfaction, which in turn affects customer loyalty.	15	23	0	5	0
Behavioural Loyalty					
A company's ability to make a profit depends heavily on the behavioral loyalty of consumers.	16	20	0	6	1
Behavioral loyalty is viewed as repeat transactions, as a percentage of all transactions, and as total spends.	13	20	0	7	3
Customer behavioral loyalty can lead to profit generation through increased market share	21	15	0	2	5
Sales promotion					
The development of sales can indicate the level of consumer demand for the company's products.	20	20	1	2	0
Companies experiencing sales growth mean that the company's products are accepted in the market and successfully compete with competitors.	14	24	0	3	2
A company usually sets performance goals in such a way that they have a clear direction to achieve the goals.	19	17	0	7	0

Source: Filed survey, 2024

Data Analysis

The table below is the descriptive statistics that was computed to show the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, maximum values, and Skewness-Kurtosis statistics, etc.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
SPM	5	1	193	73.00	84.926	.773	.913	-1.496	2.000
BHL	5	3.00	181.00	73.0000	78.03845	.693	.913	-1.733	2.000
CIL	5	3.00	188.00	73.0000	81.00617	.797	.913	-1.444	2.000
Valid N (listwise)	5								

Source: SPSS 20.0 output, 2024

The descriptive statistics for the independent variables, emotional loyalty (EML), behaviour loyalty (BHL); sales promotion (SPM) was represented in Table 2. The mean is used to establish a baseline. The maximum and

minimum numbers, on the other hand, aid in the detection of data problems. The variation from the mean is represented by the standard deviation. It is a risk indicator; the greater the standard deviation, the greater the risk. The standard deviation is a metric that expresses how much each item in a dataset deviates from the mean. It is the most reliable and extensively used metric. The standard deviations in the firms are 78.04, 81.01 and 84.93, for CPI, BHV and SPM respectively.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between corporate image loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery.

Table 3: Correlations

	SPM	CPI
Pearson Correlation	1	.959**
SPM Sig. (2-tailed)		.010
N	5	5
Pearson Correlation	.959**	1
CPI Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	
N	5	5

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Indeed, from Table 3 above, correlation coefficient of 0.96 a positive correlation between corporate image loyalty and sale promotion. To get an idea of how much variance the two variables share, the coefficient of determination (R) is calculated. R is $0.96 \times 0.96 = 92$. It implies that corporate image loyalty help to explain 92% of the variance in sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery.

Decision: From the above result, the study discovers that the confidence level between corporate image loyalty and sale promotion is very high, and that correlation coefficient is significant at 0.01 levels. Since p-value 0.010 is less than 0.01, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts alternate hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between corporate image loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between behavioural loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery.

Table 4: Correlations

	SPM	BHV
Pearson Correlation	1	.993**
SPM Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
N	5	5
Pearson Correlation	.993**	1
BHV Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
N	5	5

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Indeed, from Table 4 above, correlation coefficient of 0.99 a positive correlation between behavioural loyalty and sale promotion. To get an idea of how much variance the two variables share, the coefficient of determination (R)

is calculated. R is $0.99 \times 0.99 = 98$. It implies that behavioural loyalty help to explain 92% of the variance in sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery.

Decision: From the above result, the study discovers that the confidence level between behavioural loyalty and sale promotion is very high, and that correlation coefficient is significant at 0.01 levels. Since p-value 0.001 is less than 0.01, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts alternate hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between behavioural loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery.

Discussion and Conclusion

The study examined the association between customers' loyalty and the sales promotion of Nigerian Brewery. Data for the study were generated from the questionnaire administered to the respondents. There is a significant relationship between corporate image loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery, showing that customers are impressed about the organizational activities and these perceptions of an organization reflected in the associations held in consumer memory. Also, there is a significant relationship between behavioural loyalty and sale promotion of Nigerian Brewery. this imply that customer's behaviour are always of immense benefits to the organization, as loyal customers are so dogmatic that these customers will not switch even in the midst of the organization apparent errors. This is in disagreement with Tanveer and Hammad (2022) the results revealed that corporate image of the banks are not associated with customer loyalty, but this association is possible due to customer loyalty. The result is in agreement with Nosike and Egbunike (2022) results showed a positive significant relationship between behavioral loyalty and consumer purchase intention. The study therefore concludes that customers' loyalty and the sales promotion of Nigerian Brewery.

Based on the conclusion, the study makes the following recommendations;

1. The management should effectively determine those brands with established consumers' loyalties. Other brand specific methods of rewards should be sought and used for customers of brands with lesser loyalty.
2. The refinery is advised to further use loyalty programs as strategies for rewarding customers. This will further enhance behavioural loyalty of customers. Customers can also be engaged with periodic customer satisfaction surveys to further understand where adjustments or improvements needed to be made.

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